

Exploration of the experience of fatigue in schizophrenia in a psychosocial rehabilitation context
Supplementary materials - 2

Themes	Main categories	Categories	Sub-categories	Participants per category (%)	Participant	Quote
Descriptions of fatigue	Beliefs about fatigue	Fatigue catastrophism	Hope about the temporary nature of fatigue	41.7	1	<i>There are times, there are days when things are better, much better. So I have hope.</i>
					4	<i>I have hope, yes.</i>
					4	<i>I hope; I tell myself every time I start a day, or when I finish a day, I say to myself, 'I hope that tomorrow I'll be even better'.</i>
					4	<i>Starting from scratch means that tomorrow... that the next day, I'll be able to feel better physically. For example, every day I tell myself, 'Come on, I'm going to try to eat better, I'm going to try to eat better, I'm going to try to eat better.' And I, bit by bit, try to do a little better; even if I don't succeed, I try a little bit more every day. And if I fail, I tell myself, 'Oh no, it's a new day, I can start from scratch, I can have my shower at this time, I can choose my clothes and everything.' So, bit by bit, little by little, I manage to do small things, but they are good.</i>
					5	<i>I hope it will stop one day because I can't take it anymore...</i>
					6	<i>I hope so.</i>
					9	<i>When I pray, when I have a glimmer of hope that things will get better</i>
					9	<i>there may be hope that things will get better in the future</i>
			Fatalism about the immutable nature of fatigue	41.7	2	<i>Not on my own, anyway.</i>
					3	<i>No, not if I don't rest</i>
					5	<i>But fatigue is something you can't really do much about.</i>
					7	<i>Unless they find a miracle drug, I think it'll always be there, given that the illness can't be cured. Well, it can be treated, but it can't be cured.</i>

		Distinction between good and bad fatigue		16.7	8	<i>What can I do, honestly? No, I can't do anything, can't do anything</i>
				3	<i>Bad fatigue is when you haven't slept all night, I think. And when you sit around thinking and don't do anything, don't get on with your day.</i>	
				3	<i>Good fatigue, yes.</i>	
				3	<i>Eating well, sleeping well, perhaps reading a book—these things are important. They generate good fatigue</i>	
				8	<i>I feel tired, I'm happy.</i>	
				8	<i>even even though fatigue is fundamentally bad</i>	
				8	<i>Bad fatigue is when you fall asleep after midnight. [...] Good fatigue is when you fall asleep around 9, between 9 and 10.</i>	
		Distinction between physical and mental fatigue	Differences in physical and mental fatigue	50	1	<i>Physical and mental. (.....)</i>
					3	<i>It doesn't have the same effect on your mind and the energy you have for the day.</i>
					3	<i>It depends on the activities: whether they were physical, sporting, or more intellectual, like after reading a book.</i>
					3	<i>It depends on the day you've had, on the night you've had.</i>
					6	<i>Mental fatigue and physical fatigue.</i>
					9	<i>I'm more mentally tired than physically tired.</i>
					11	<i>There's physical fatigue and mental fatigue.</i>
					11	<i>The body and the mental.</i>
Distinction between physical and mental fatigue	Similarities between physical and mental fatigue	33.3	2	<i>When I feel one, I feel the other.</i>		
			2	<i>A mental and physical state, of muscle perception</i>		
			4	<i>A slowing down of... physically and also mentally.</i>		

					7	<i>Mental fatigue and physical fatigue</i>
					11	<i>For me, it's the mind: when it's tired and that affects the body</i>
			Specificities of mental fatigue	66.7	1	<i>mental [fatigue] is when I don't have clear thoughts</i>
					2	<i>It tires me out a bit mentally too.</i>
					2	<i>And psychologically as well, because I'd really like to spend another two hours in bed</i>
					2	<i>mental fatigue is more like the day after football, the next morning. When I wake up, I'm a bit dazed, my head's spinning a bit, like I haven't slept enough.</i>
					3	<i>It takes me a while to think and all that; I feel like my brain needs to rest.</i>
					3	<i>Often it's the brain that doesn't feel like it.</i>
					6	<i>And the psychological aspect is more about the mental load.</i>
					7	<i>And mental fatigue is more about hallucinations, being overwhelmed by voices.</i>
					7	<i>Mental fatigue is more, um, for example, I don't feel like doing things, thinking about things.</i>
					9	<i>A kind of moral fatigue.</i>
					10	<i>Actually, fatigue, as I told you, has caused a sense of instability and so, well, it makes you overthink.</i>
					10	<i>Fatigue is in the mind.</i>
					10	<i>Fatigue makes my mind overthink.</i>
					12	<i>Psychological fatigue is the brain sending signals to the body, telling it, 'Right, you need to take it easy now,' sort of thing</i>
			Specificities of physical fatigue	58.3	1	<i>It's when I can't manage physical effort, when I find it hard to exert myself.</i>
					2	<i>Muscle-wise.</i>
					2	<i>A physical slowness</i>
					2	<i>I feel all my muscles... getting... disrupted,</i>

					2	<i>when [the muscles] cool down, I've really felt them working and then all my energy just drains away</i>
					2	<i>[physical fatigue] is a physical state that the body has endured and needs to eliminate</i>
					2	<i>[the muscles] they've worked hard, basically. They're more tense than usual.</i>
					2	<i>I can feel that my muscles have been working,</i>
					3	<i>There are types of fatigue where it's the body that's tired.</i>
					4	<i>... I think it's mainly physically that I have a problem. Because, given the body I have and everything, it takes a lot more physical effort to move around, to get up and to carry out daily activities.</i>
					4	<i>Fatigue is more of a sensation, yes, quite a physical sensation that you can feel in your body... where you don't feel like doing anything.</i>
					6	<i>Physical fatigue comes after exertion or being awake for a bit too long.</i>
					7	<i>Physical fatigue is about making an effort; it's as if my muscles are suffering, really.</i>
					7	<i>Physical fatigue, I can feel my body getting out of breath, getting out of breath</i>
					11	<i>Physical fatigue</i>
					11	<i>If I have to climb stairs, I'm not as strong as usual.</i>
					11	<i>Physical fatigue is mainly when I do an activity like a very long hike; then, yes, there will be physical fatigue.</i>
					Manifestations of fatigue	Sensations
Slowness	16.7	1	<i>difficulty moving, a lack of motivation.</i>			
Heaviness	50	2	<i>It's, how can I put it, a slowness.</i>			
					1	<i>Stenosing, I don't know.</i>

					1	<i>There's a weight. There's a heaviness, everything's hard... I don't know, it's hard.</i>
					1	<i>Yes, you could compare it to a weight, yes</i>
					2	<i>I feel a bit heavier than usual.</i>
					4	<i>It's a feeling that our body is heavy.</i>
					4	<i>Fatigue is a feeling of heaviness... psychologically, in the brain.</i>
					4	<i>It's a physical heaviness, but certainly a mental heaviness too</i>
					4	<i>this feeling that I'm a bit heavy, it affects my brain.</i>
					4	<i>when I get out of bed, I feel a physical heaviness, which takes a lot of energy, not just to get out of bed, but also to start the day. Normally, well personally, normally, you're supposed to get up and have a bit of energy to start the day. I said that... that in the morning, I feel more refreshed, but the start is very, very, very difficult for me because I feel there's a barrier when I get up. There's a barrier telling me 'I'm too tired'.</i>
					4	<i>A feeling of heaviness, and you don't really have the energy to want to do physical or mental activities because you feel a barrier, a sort of heaviness in your body</i>
					5	<i>I feel heavy. (.....) Laziness,</i>
					5	<i>Feeling... unable to hold myself up properly and all that...</i>
					5	<i>I feel heavy and tired of doing nothing. But I don't actually have the strength to do it.</i>
					5	<i>Especially the upper body; I feel like I'm weighing heavily there.</i>
					6	<i>Heaviness.</i>
					8	<i>You feel heavy</i>
					3	<i>I feel all limp, a bit sluggish in my body.</i>
			Sluggishness	16.7	12	<i>It's like being a bit flabby, really.</i>
					9	<i>Stiffness everywhere.</i>
			Stiffness	8.3	9	<i>Excruciating muscle tension</i>

			Being worn out	33.3	6	<i>Wearing me down.</i>
					6	<i>It's wearing me down. You can feel it working away</i>
					7	<i>I would say that I am, I am worn out, basically. It's kind of like wear and tear, because when I was a kid, I wasn't like that.</i>
					7	<i>'Wear and tear from the illness.</i>
					7	<i>Fatigue is being worn out.</i>
					9	<i>There's a lot of wearing out.</i>
					11	<i>It's not a kind of fatigue where I can't do anything anymore. It's just a sensation.</i>
			Lack of energy	16.7	1	<i>It's a lack of vital energy.</i>
					1	<i>A lack of Chi</i>
					1	<i>A lack of vital energy, in fact</i>
					3	<i>It also describes a lack of energy for carrying out activities</i>
					3	<i>And fatigue where you don't have the desire or the energy to do things.</i>
					8	<i>I have a certain amount of stamina, but at a certain point, I run out of mental energy.</i>
					8	<i>At a certain point, when your batteries run out, well, you just stop functioning, like a robot that's empty.</i>
					12	<i>When you can't manage it, you don't have the energy to do it.</i>
			Lack of envy	16.7	9	<i>A loss of motivation.</i>
					12	<i>At the moment, I don't do much. No, that's for sure. (.....) There's a saying that goes: the less you do, the less you feel like doing anything, actually.</i>
					12	<i>Fatigue is just not wanting to do anything, really</i>
			Sleep	58.3	3	<i>there are times when you're so tired you need to get some sleep.</i>
					4	<i>It's just that our brains, my eyes, they're all heavy, they all want to shut down</i>
					6	<i>The urge to sleep.</i>

					6	<i>It's when you struggle to stay focused, when you feel you're going to fall asleep any minute, when your eyelids are heavy, and you pay less and less attention to what's going on around you</i>
					8	<i>Fatigue, that's it, it's the body saying, "OK, now go lie down, get some sleep, 7 hours, or 8, or 9, when you've had enough... you're not sleepy anymore</i>
					8	<i>The eyelids, yes, which...</i>
					9	<i>Sleeping standing up</i>
					9	<i>Tiredness is wanting to sleep.</i>
					12	<i>Wanting to go to sleep, basically.</i>
					2	<i>I feel like I haven't had enough rest, actually.</i>
					3	<i>Sometimes I'm so tired I can't sleep.</i>
					12	<i>It's when you think about the night, right, even though it's morning.</i>
			Effort	58.3	1	<i>It's because you have to make an effort for everything... When I'm tired, I have to... it takes effort, yeah.</i>
					4	<i>there's a feeling of tiredness. It's a feeling of exertion. But it's not the kind of exertion that... well, I'm saying normal people... it's not the kind of exertion they feel, which I think is less intense for them, which requires less... effort.</i>
					6	<i>And when I'm really tired, that's when I start to struggle with those activities.</i>
					6	<i>when I make an effort to walk, to travel</i>
					6	<i>a mental effort, quite simply.</i>
					7	<i>It is having to make an effort to do normal things.</i>
					7	<i>when I have to do something.</i>
					9	<i>For me, fatigue is when you have put in effort</i>
					11	<i>It's physically difficult, even when I'm walking</i>
					12	<i>You think about the effort you have to make and you tell yourself it's too much</i>

		Dissociation		33.3	9	<i>I couldn't hear what you were saying. Researcher: OK. You were there, but you weren't really there. Participant: There you go. So, I don't really understand much of it. Maybe that... maybe we can define it like that too.</i>
					11	<i>It's as if I'd been hypnotised.</i>
		Increased symptoms of schizophrenia	Positive symptoms	8.3	10	<i>I'm feeling unsteady, I don't know if it's a bit of paranoia or what</i>
					10	<i>Yes, because tiredness creates a sense of unsteadiness.</i>
					10	<i>When I'm tired and haven't slept, I'm unsettled, but... unsettled, you know.</i>
					10	<i>When I'm tired, I'm unsettled.</i>
			Negative symptoms	16.7	9	<i>There's a lot of demoralisation</i>
					9	<i>there's a lot of pessimism</i>
					10	<i>Fear</i>
					10	<i>anxiety</i>
	Qualification of fatigue	Constance		75	10	<i>Yes, anxiety.</i>
					3	<i>I often feel tired on a daily basis</i>
					3	<i>It's part of my routine now, in fact, part of my everyday life.</i>
					3	<i>It's a state of mind, a mood that's quite... that affects my daily life</i>
					4	<i>It's just a constant feeling of... a continuous sensation of... I don't know how to explain this hindrance, but it's a continuous feeling every day of... of exhaustion, really.</i>
		4	<i>Like everyone else, there are good days and there are bad days</i>			
		5	<i>It is always there.</i>			
		6	<i>That's it, it's a constant presence, actually.</i>			
		7	<i>Ever since I fell ill... 20 years, 18-20 years</i>			
		7	<i>No, it's always the same.</i>			

				7	<i>But I'm not terribly tired during the day, you know. [...] It's a constant tiredness that's always there, but I force myself to do activities, well, a few of them, anyway.</i>
				7	<i>Otherwise, it's always the same. The fatigue doesn't really decrease.</i>
				9	<i>Actually, I've got so used to it that I don't even ask myself the question anymore, really.</i>
				9	<i>Actually, yes, I've got so used to the generalised weakness that I can't even tell anymore... That's it, that's why I'm a bit lost right now. I'm so used to this generalised weakness that I don't know anymore.</i>
				9	<i>It's linear</i>
				9	<i>Right now, it's chronic fatigue caused by the medication</i>
				10	<i>Yes, it's always the same</i>
				11	<i>It's just a way of life, really. You have to fight against it all the time, you know.</i>
				11	<i>Pretty much all the time.</i>
				11	<i>The fatigue is going to stay.</i>
				12	<i>Yeah, I think... it's, it's manageable, really.</i>
	Subsequent to an occupation	33.3	2	<i>After work.</i>	
			2	<i>Physical fatigue, well, I feel that in the morning too, or rather in the evening, after training.</i>	
			2	<i>Generally when work finishes... the working day, I've felt it go by, really. I'm less fit than when I go in. I'd love a nap after work, really.</i>	
			2	<i>After work, it's more physical fatigue too</i>	
			2	<i>Most of the time, I leave work feeling tired</i>	
			2	<i>During the effort, actually, from time to time, I feel a bit of a slackening. And that's how I gauge how tired I'm going to be or how tired I actually am.</i>	

				2	<i>When I'm making the effort, actually, my muscles are warm. And I don't feel the tiredness straight away.</i>		
				2	<i>Once you've done some exercise, well, you can feel that you've really worked your muscles.</i>		
				3	<i>After the activities I did during the day.</i>		
				4	<i>It's the same when you take a shower or do anything that requires a bit of effort; you feel very worn out.</i>		
				4	<i>When I get home, I'm absolutely exhausted. And then, I have this heaviness in my head telling me, 'I can't take any more'.</i>		
				11	<i>Now, with classes starting up again, I was tired in the morning</i>		
	Tediousness			33.3	3	<i>So it's a bit of a nuisance, really.</i>	
					4	<i>My brain says, 'Oh, I'm too tired, I can't, I can't get out of bed.' That's it, it's very embarrassing</i>	
					5	<i>fatigue is a bother</i>	
					5	<i>it's a bother. I'm fed up with doing nothing</i>	
					11	<i>It's a handicap.</i>	
	Variations in fatigue intensity	Increased fatigue post treatment		16.7	1	<i>After a week, I usually feel better.</i>	
					1	<i>On the first day after the injection, I'm much more tired.</i>	
					6	<i>When I stay awake too long after taking my medication</i>	
		Daily variations	More fatigue in the mornings		41.7	1	<i>Usually, by the afternoon, I feel better.</i>
						1	<i>In the morning.</i>
						4	<i>In the morning, just after waking up, like everyone else, I am very, very, very tired.</i>
4						<i>At the start, it's very, very, very difficult for me because I feel like there's a barrier when I get up. There's a barrier telling me, 'I'm too tired'.</i>	
4		<i>But I find that perhaps because of my illness, when you get up, you really feel a barrier stopping you from wanting to get up in the morning.</i>					

					4	<i>It's really a barrier in the morning and for doing normal activities for some people, for most people. But for us, I think that with the illness, it's really, it's more important.</i>				
					4	<i>When I get out of bed, I have... Normally, you're supposed to get out of bed feeling energetic and rested. But I find that perhaps because of my illness, when you get up, you really feel a barrier stopping you from wanting to get up in the morning.</i>				
					4	<i>Getting up from a nap... it's still morning, it's like morning, it's exactly the same as in the morning. It takes a lot of effort.</i>				
					5	<i>It's just that we can't get up to... I don't know how to put it, to do things, to have goals</i>				
					10	<i>That... that... that comes... it comes in the morning when I've just woken up.</i>				
					12	<i>In the morning when I get up.</i>				
					12	<i>Morning tiredness is because you're bored, so you're still a bit... a bit sleepy,</i>				
					4	<i>I'm actually quite fit in the morning, I'd say.</i>				
			Less fatigue in the mornings		25	4	<i>But from about 10 o'clock until lunch, I have a burst of energy</i>			
						4	<i>in the morning, it's a time when it's a bit more... a bit more energetic</i>			
						6	<i>In the morning, it's fine. Because I've just woken up, I'm feeling fit</i>			
						10	<i>Yes, after I wake up, after that, slowly, slowly, it gets better.</i>			
						More fatigue around midday		33.3	3	<i>After lunch, generally. There's a bit of a slump.</i>
									3	<i>I'd say that with the treatment I'm on now and the sleeping pills I have to take in the evening and at night, I'm often tired in the afternoon; after lunch, I need to have a nap.</i>
									4	<i>And afterwards, once I've digested, I feel exhausted.</i>

				1	<i>The light, perhaps.</i>
				12	<i>When it's sunny, it's better, really.</i>
Consequences of fatigue on daily living	Negative impact on activities	Less activities compared to the period before fatigue	33.3	5	<i>It was the cooking, because, well, when you have a flat, you cook every day.</i>
				6	<i>I do fewer things.</i>
				6	<i>There are things I used to do that I don't have the strength to do now.</i>
				6	<i>Just doing one of the tasks I used to do seems like a huge effort to me.</i>
				7	<i>The fact that I'm more inactive, you know</i>
				10	<i>all the activities, in fact, that take place outdoors, you avoid them because... Participant R07A: [00:15:59] No, I don't avoid them. I still do them. But less than before.</i>
				10	<i>Especially at the moment, I do fewer activities than before</i>
				4	<i>What I'd really like to do is take part in more sporting activities.</i>
	Barrier to physical activity	50	4	<i>I had this tiredness, I had this heaviness, I had this barrier holding me back. And I was exhausted. I... It... It... It was getting in the way. And since then, it's got worse. I couldn't do physical activity like I used to. Not because of my body. But because I was... I was on medication</i>	
			4	<i>with the fatigue, it's really a hindrance because you really don't feel very motivated to carry on.</i>	
			6	<i>Doing sport.</i>	
			7	<i>Because of physical fatigue, yes, I don't do any sports</i>	
			8	<i>Boxing, hitting the bags</i>	
9	<i>So improving your mobility, it seems? Participant : Exactly. That... Exactly. It's physically draining, that. Researcher: OK. So that's something you've given up, for example? Participant: Yeah.</i>				

				10	<i>Yes, fitness trails. I used to do fitness trails. I don't do them anymore.</i>
		Barriers to routines	41.7	3	<i>It stops you from getting on with the day</i>
				4	<i>the daily hygiene routine.</i>
				4	<i>the care you need to give your body.</i>
				4	<i>It leaves us with less energy to do normal activities.</i>
				4	<i>It's the routines.</i>
				4	<i>Everyday things.</i>
				4	<i>It's very, very, very hard to carry on with the rest of my daily routine</i>
				7	<i>Just taking a shower, walking... I'm just tired all the time, really.</i>
				9	<i>My lifestyle is dreadful. //Investigator: OK.// It's rubbish</i>
				11	<i>It'd become hard to hold down a job.</i>
				Barrier to performing desired activities	25
		4	<i>Well, you can't do all the everyday things you enjoy doing without help.</i>		
		4	<i>It's not that I don't want to do them, it's just that... I can't.</i>		
		12	<i>I can't do what I want, you know</i>		
		Barriers to crafting activities	16.7	3	<i>pottery, art... playing a game of pétanque, loads of activities</i>
				11	<i>It's impossible to play the guitar when you're tired; it's too complicated</i>
		Barriers to activities in general	41.7	2	<i>Worst case, I just don't do it. Best case, I put it off until I'm a bit less tired, basically.</i>
				3	<i>which stops me doing my activities, but I do them anyway</i>
				4	<i>So, I sleep and that... It really gets in the way of my afternoon activities, especially.</i>
				8	<i>I don't have a lot of time to act, to do things.</i>
				11	<i>I can't do everything. In September, I started too many things.</i>

	Time spent inactive/resting	50	2	<i>More time to rest.</i>
			3	<i>To stay awake.</i>
			3	<i>I'm too tired for that, so I rather rest instead</i>
			5	<i>Well, I don't do anything.</i>
			5	<i>I spend a lot of time in my bed</i>
			6	<i>I sleep a lot</i>
			11	<i>As a result, I've stopped everything</i>
			12	<i>Staying in bed and just waiting for the day to pass, basically.</i>
	Barrier to autonomy outside of the institution	25	4	<i>Going for a walk outside sometimes, well... going for a walk... having... the motivation to do things outside.</i>
			6	<i>Taking long journeys on my own.</i>
			10	<i>I don't go to the village as often as I used to.</i>
			10	<i>Yeah, going out.</i>
	Barrier to social interactions	16.7	6	<i>[Less] Open to social interaction.</i>
			6	<i>Yeah. Actually, it's a bit like morning tiredness making you grumpy, except here it's mental fatigue that makes you grumpy.</i>
			6	<i>I'm available for less of the day.</i>
			6	<i>When I'm mentally tired, I can be a bit short, a bit less friendly.</i>
			7	<i>Yeah, socialising, it just gets too hard after a while, you know.</i>
			7	<i>Socialising.</i>
			7	<i>Just saying hello, going out with the group, that's fine. But having friends or things like that, I've stopped</i>
	Decreased enjoyment	8.3	1	<i>Enjoying the daytime activities.</i>
1			<i>It stops me from enjoying the good things.</i>	
Slowing	25	6	<i>I'm a bit slower</i>	

				25	11	<i>I can't keep up with everyone else.</i>
					12	<i>Let's say it slows me down a bit</i>
					2	<i>Forgetting things, yeah, I'm too tired, so I don't do it on purpose.</i>
					2	<i>I do forget certain things sometimes, yeah.</i>
					7	<i>The fact that I'm so overloaded... I just can't think straight.</i>
					9	<i>Tiredness affects how I interpret things too, so it's complicated.</i>
Fatigue management strategies	Decreasing fatigue/increasing energy	Consuming something	Caffeine consumption	50	2	<i>I'll get a Monster from Carrefour and drink it, that way... my energy levels go up a bit.</i>
					3	<i>I often have a cup of coffee after lunch as well.</i>
					3	<i>Sometimes I have breakfast with a cup of coffee.</i>
					8	<i>Even after a coffee, sometimes I'm tired, I'm just so tired... I've got no energy left</i>
					8	<i>Apart from some dark chocolate, or... a coffee that gives me a headache</i>
					9	<i>are there things that help you, perhaps, to reduce your daily tiredness? Participant : Coffee, yes.</i>
					9	<i>Coffee doesn't really wake me up much anymore</i>
					11	<i>Drinking a coffee, perhaps</i>
		12	<i>Drinking coffee.</i>			
		Other	25	3	<i>Drinking a bit</i>	
				3	<i>Eating something</i>	
				11	<i>Drinking a glass of water,</i>	
				12	<i>Eating kiwis.</i>	
		Resting	Sleeping	33.3	2	<i>Either I rest a bit, or I wait until the evening to go to bed really early and get a great night's sleep.</i>
					3	<i>I try to sleep well at night.</i>
6	<i>I sleep.</i>					

			Taking a nap	33.3	7	<i>Apart from sleeping.</i>
					3	<i>I usually have a little nap after lunch, in the afternoon</i>
					3	<i>I need to have my nap.</i>
					3	<i>I might have to take a nap.</i>
					3	<i>that I take a nap</i>
					4	<i>in the afternoon, after a nap, I feel re-...rejuvenated.</i>
					4	<i>I take a nap; normally, you feel even more energetic. But even if it's 30 minutes or 20 minutes, I often don't feel... re-energised</i>
					4	<i>And after the afternoon, I need to... recharge my batteries, with a little nap or something like that. And then, in the afternoon, after a nap, I feel re-...renewed. And there you go, I manage to get things done.</i>
					6	<i>It's through micro-naps, actually.</i>
					6	<i>When I'm really tired, I can have a nap for an hour, an hour and a half, two hours.</i>
					10	<i>I just have a nap at... around 2 pm. A nap lasting no more than 45 minutes. And afterwards, well, but the nap does me good when I have it. Because when I have a nap, I recover a bit.</i>
			10	<i>Nap is more for my own well-being.</i>		
			10	<i>When I have a nap, actually, I have a nap, it feels good. I wake up, it feels good, but it doesn't last long</i>		
			Taking time to rest/relax	41.7	1	<i>Er... I rest.</i>
					1	<i>I sit down on... I sit down on a chair and... I sit still</i>
					2	<i>I try to rest as much as possible, actually.</i>
					2	<i>I spend half an hour, an hour in bed trying to rest. Afterwards, I feel better</i>
					3	<i>you need a good rest as well.</i>
					3	<i>I just wait a little while</i>

				10	<i>Yes, it helps with my tiredness.</i>
				10	<i>I take showers.</i>
				10	<i>Lying quietly in bed. [...] Everything switched off, settling down quietly in bed, lying down. That's it. I wait for my emotions and everything to fade away.</i>
				11	<i>That's why I lie down in bed, trying to untangle myself from my thoughts</i>
				11	<i>You need to settle down</i>
		Beneficial effect of treatments	16.7	9	<i>I'm lucky to have the antidepressant that stimulates me; otherwise, I could be completely out of it.</i>
				9	<i>If I didn't have antidepressants, well, it would be... It wouldn't even be worth it. I'd be completely out cold</i>
				9	<i>I have the antidepressants, though, which help me a lot.</i>
				11	<i>When I have too many thoughts, now, I tell myself that Loxapac is a good medicine.</i>
		Spirituality	8.3	9	<i>When it comes to prayers, it gives me a boost of energy, yes</i>
	9			<i>When I'm struggling with day-to-day life, with my daily life, the act of hoping gives me a boost of energy.</i>	
	Distracting oneself from fatigue	Cognitive activities	33.3	3	<i>doing [cognitive] exercises</i>
				3	<i>I do Sudoku puzzles or mental exercises</i>
				8	<i>Meditation is a bit like, just a tiny bit like sleeping, as we were talking about earlier; it's recharging your batteries a little bit, and in the mornings I get up, and... that's it.</i>
				11	<i>Writing, lying in bed.</i>
				12	<i>You need to keep your mind occupied,</i>
		Passive activities	33.3	3	<i>I watch a movie from time to time.</i>
				3	<i>I put on some music precisely for that... I settle down in bed. It helps me switch off and clear my mind a bit.</i>

				6	<i>When I'm tired, just a little bit, I can still do things that let me rest without sleeping.</i>
				7	<i>Relax, watch a film, but it's more of a passive thing, really.</i>
				7	<i>When I'm enjoying listening to music or watching a film, I stop thinking about fatigue, you know</i>
				11	<i>Watching just one movie makes me think of something else.</i>
		Crafting activities	8.3	4	<i>And after a few minutes, I'm fully immersed and I forget my problems and I forget all that. Interviewer: And so, you forget your tiredness too? Participant: I feel the tiredness, but it's much less intense.</i>
				4	<i>Especially art or pottery, which are very manually-oriented and relax my brain</i>
		Physical activities	33.3	1	<i>I need to move around otherwise... I need physical exercise</i>
				1	<i>I've got a skipping rope too, for the morning, to get me going... that might help me</i>
				1	<i>I do physical activities. [...] As much as possible.</i>
				1	<i>There are exercises to release vital energy.</i>
				3	<i>Going to the gym too.</i>
				3	<i>Getting some exercise now and then, going out, having a walk.</i>
				4	<i>I'd say sport, of course... sport and activities.</i>
				4	<i>When I exercise, I feel that my muscles, my body are much lighter</i>
				4	<i>It takes effort and it's tiring, but at the same time, I feel as though I'm in a little cocoon, very... very good. Because afterwards, I feel really good.</i>
5	<i>Walking, I find that energises me.</i>				
5	<i>You're in better shape when you walk than when you sleep. I mean, just sleeping is a bad. How do you say it? Researcher: a vicious circle? Participant: a vicious circle</i>				
Forcing oneself to be active	16.7	7	<i>I force myself to do things, I force myself</i>		

			41.7	11	<i>No, I force myself.</i>
				11	<i>I force myself to do things.</i>
		Keeping busy		1	<i>I have to do lots of things during the day, otherwise I'm not... happy.</i>
				4	<i>With activities that are a bit more free-form and in a slightly calmer environment, I feel much more recharged.</i>
				4	<i>When I started doing activities, that's when the tiredness just disappears.</i>
				5	<i>Keeping myself busy... it keeps me awake, let's say. [...] It keeps me awake with a purpose, a certain purpose.</i>
				5	<i>The key is to keep yourself busy, to not sit around doing nothing</i>
				11	<i>At the end of the day, it's better when you're active</i>
				12	<i>You're busy doing something else, so you manage to, to get the better of it, sort of.</i>
				12	<i>Keeping busy.</i>
	Ignoring fatigue	5	<i>I don't deal with it.</i>		
		5	<i>It's not easy to manage the tiredness. Either it's there, or it's not, but you just get on with it, either way.</i>		
		9	<i>Ah, I've given up completely</i>		
		11	<i>I do things without paying attention to fatigue</i>		
		12	<i>I try not to think about it, for a start. [...] Participant: To put it aside.</i>		
	Pacing strategies	Planning activities and rest	16.7	3	<i>I've adopted a schedule to manage this fatigue, a timetable</i>
				3	<i>What I do is try to get everything done when I need to. That way, at least, I can rest afterwards. And I know it's been done.</i>
				3	<i>Because I've either got the afternoon off or the morning off, and that gives me a bit of time to recharge.</i>

		Establishing routines	8.3	3	<i>I think it's important to have a good daily routine... to eat three meals a day, do a bit of exercise now and then, do some mental activities, read a book... do word searches, crosswords, Sudokus. Having these daily activities helps to build up energy for the day. To have energy.</i>
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Supplementary table 1 : *Experience of fatigue in people with schizophrenia with participants' quotes*

Theme	Main categories	Categories	Sub-categories	Participants per category (%)	Participant	Quote
Factors causing fatigue	Schizophrenia	Treatment		66.7	1	<i>I've never felt as tired as I have since I started this treatment</i>
					1	<i>It's like a straitjacket, actually—a chemical straitjacket, I don't know how to put it.</i>
					1	<i>The treatment... the treatment makes me tired.</i>
					3	<i>It's mainly the treatment I'm taking</i>
					3	<i>It treats my illness, but it also deprives me of my energy for the whole day</i>
					3	<i>I have less energy; I think it's because of taking the treatment every day.</i>
					3	<i>The fact of digesting all that, the treatment. (...) And taking the if-needed medication in the evening, and all that—it tires the body out.</i>
					3	<i>The fact of digesting all the medication slows me down a bit, both physically and mentally. I don't overthink things as much, but in the end, I'm a bit slower.</i>
					3	<i>taking the daily treatment</i>
					4	<i>When I first took medication, I had this feeling of being held back.</i>
					4	<i>It's tiring, isn't it.</i>
					7	<i>the medication</i>
					7	<i>taking medication as well.</i>
					7	<i>the medication I've been taking all the time for years</i>
					8	<i>The treatment has worn me out</i>
					9	<i>The medication just knocks you out, you know.</i>
9	<i>[Fatigue] is dictated by the antipsychotics; they control sleep. I'm always fighting against it. So there, yes, it's worn me out a bit.</i>					
9	<i>A tiredness linked to a psychoactive substance, so I'm not naturally tired</i>					
9	<i>Researcher: You're also fighting against the effects of the treatments; well, does that exhaust you too? Participant: Yes, yes. Right now, yes, yes.</i>					

				11	<i>The treatments are tiring too.</i>	
				12	<i>But it's true that when you add extra pills or whatever, it's true that it...</i>	
				12	<i>with my pills, it's true that it's very tiring,</i>	
				12	<i>when I started taking the treatment, I was knackered,</i>	
		Fatigue is a symptom of schizophrenia		33.3	1	<i>The illness</i>
					3	<i>Yes, it's a consequence.</i>
					3	<i>Yes, I think it could be a symptom [of schizophrenia].</i>
					3	<i>It's something that becomes part of daily life because of the illness, and you have to know how to... take a lot of medication and all that to look after yourself so you can move on. [...]</i>
					3	<i>It's part of [schizophrenia], I think.</i>
					7	<i>The illness</i>
					7	<i>the illness.</i>
		Positive symptoms	Hallucinations	16.7	5	<i>Well, yes, being on edge all the time, talking to voices and all that</i>
					7	<i>Having hallucinations, it exhausts me psychologically</i>
			Delusions	8.3	10	<i>Delusions</i>
					10	<i>Does it take a lot of energy, for example, to manage the delusions? Participant: Yes, it takes energy, yes, yes, yes</i>
		Negative symptoms	Disorganisation	8.3	10	<i>delusions.</i>
					9	<i>Complete disorganisation</i>
					9	<i>It's the disorganisation. If there were any organisation... That too takes a lot of energy</i>
			Other symptoms	8.3	9	<i>disorganisation plays a part too.</i>
					1	<i>I'm not thinking clearly, so to speak.</i>
					1	<i>The lack of motivation.</i>
			1	<i>The symptoms of the... the symptoms.</i>		

		Life course associated with the disease	Frequent hospitalizations	16.7	1	<i>My story. [...] I haven't had a normal life, let's say</i>	
					7	<i>And I have been hospitalized for years. [...] So, I think it wears me down more than a normal person.</i>	
					7	<i>The fact of being in hospital all the time, of not being able to have a flat.</i>	
					7	<i>The hospital stays, not having... In terms of the wear and tear, the fatigue, not having a normal, settled life.</i>	
					7	<i>The fact that I'm always ill, in hospital – well, that plays a part too, you know.</i>	
					7	<i>Because of all the hospital stays</i>	
				Rupture with the pre-schizophrenia lifestyle	8.3	6	<i>I don't want to say that the medication is making me tired, because that would be a bit too easy. But also because starting treatment coincided with me giving up my studies, giving up sport, giving up reading because reading is difficult.</i>
						6	<i>A change in lifestyle, really, more than just treatment.</i>
	Social factors		Social interactions are tiring		25	3	<i>Coming across lots of people all day long.</i>
						4	<i>Yes, it leads to fatigue, a lot of fatigue. It makes me... By the end of the day, I'm absolutely exhausted. But not... I mean normal people, but not like some people who, when they get home, are on the sofa, feeling fine and all that. But me, when I get home, I'm absolutely exhausted. And then, I have this heaviness in my head telling me, "I can't take any more".</i>
4						<i>The noise, people saying "How are you? How are you?" and all that... And you just want to say "But I'm tired!", and then they say "Why?", and I don't want to say why!</i>	
4						<i>It affects my tiredness because... Well, when I go shopping, to buy things at the pharmacy or whatever. But I feel like... People, I see them, they carry on with their lives, they do whatever they want. But I always need to be vigilant and on my guard to... Because I feel like there's pressure on me when I go out.</i>	

				9	<i>I'm empathising, it's different.[...] That too, that's it. Something that drains my energy.</i>
				9	<i>It makes you want to scream down the corridor, "Have you finished [unintelligible]?" Researcher: OK, so holding yourself back from, say, going out into the corridor to scream—does that take energy? Participant: Oh yeah, yeah, yeah.</i>
		Lack of social interactions is tiring	25	3	<i>The fact of not seeing your friends.</i>
				9	<i>The absence of family, family for a decade</i>
				9	<i>Withdrawal into oneself, one might add.</i>
				11	<i>I get bored being alone, actually.</i>
	Agoraphobia	8.3	9	<i>Avoiding others.</i>	
			9	<i>But with agoraphobia, there's nothing you can do.</i>	
	Psychological factors	Stress	16.7	8	<i>There's a bit of stress. There's a bit of stress. After everything that's happened, I'm afraid it'll start all over again, that I'll struggle even more to sleep, that it'll all start again. Because it's all hanging by a thread. It's hanging by a thread, and bloody hell, it really scares me that it'll start all over again.</i>
				9	<i>No hope in sight of finding a place where I can feel at ease. There's a lot of fear of not finding it, a huge fear of not finding a place on the horizon where I can settle down. And that really messes me up, actually.</i>
				9	<i>Anxiety can drain your energy. That really drains your energy.</i>
		Depression	16.7	1	<i>It's depression.</i>
				1	<i>Moral</i>
				3	<i>Depression</i>
Guilt		8.3	9	<i>Researcher: Does guilt tire you out as well? Participant: Oh yeah, well then... that's it.</i>	
			9	<i>That's energy-sapping too, guilt.</i>	

		Procrastination		8.3	3	<i>If I'm tired, I put things off, and I'll end up even more tired.</i>		
					3	<i>Procrastination</i>		
					3	<i>If I put it off, put it off, put it off... And eventually... if you put everything off, you start to build up a certain weariness. In your body and your mind.</i>		
	Physiological factors	Aging		25	1	<i>My age</i>		
					7	<i>wear and tear [...] I'm starting to get old.</i>		
					7	<i>Both physical and mental [aging].</i>		
					11	<i>I feel that the older I get, the more tired I am</i>		
		Physical illness		16.7	1	<i>Internal health issues.</i>		
					1	<i>iron deficiency</i>		
					1	<i>An inner balance, I think.</i>		
					8	<i>A neurological problem.</i>		
		Sleep disorders		Sleep quality	16.7	3	<i>If I haven't slept very well during the night, I know that the next day I'll be tired.</i>	
						3	<i>The quality of sleep.</i>	
						10	<i>It depends on the night, actually, on whether I've slept well.</i>	
				Insomnia		8.3	3	<i>The fact that I suffer from insomnia.</i>
							3	<i>Perhaps insomnia.</i>
							3	<i>Lack of sleep, or insomnia,</i>
(in)activity	Making an effort		58.3	2	<i>Excessive exercise</i>			
				2	<i>The effort, the intensity of the effort we put into... into the session, well, how can I put it... during training or the class.</i>			
				3	<i>The more mental overload I have, the more tired I am afterwards.</i>			
				3	<i>I put energy into these activities. And it took a lot of effort. So, afterwards, I feel tired.</i>			

				4	<i>Reading a book is a pleasure; I wouldn't say that. But when you're colouring in or when you... Even very easy things, well, when you concentrate for a few minutes, afterwards you feel exhausted.</i>	
				6	<i>I'm not used to doing much activity, so I get tired quickly.</i>	
				7	<i>Making an effort.</i>	
				11	<i>But then, yes, afterwards, there's a real sense of tiredness.</i>	
				12	<i>Work, for example. When you're working.[...] At work, you can feel tired. [Linked] to physical exertion.</i>	
		Doing nothing		50	1	<i>A lack of stimulation too, a lack of activities, of stimulation.</i>
					5	<i>Oh no, with this cycle of... I've got nothing to do, so I do nothing, so I sleep. That drags you down. That's not going to encourage me.</i>
					5	<i>That's what tires me out the most, I find[...] It's having nothing to do</i>
					5	<i>And staying there doing nothing, well, it's a vicious circle. Getting more and more tired, tired of doing nothing</i>
					5	<i>"[...] doing nothing is a vicious circle: I'm exhausted, but without doing anything</i>
					5	<i>What tires me out is doing nothing and lying there, because I've got nothing to do.</i>
					5	<i>Doing nothing, that's tiring</i>
5					<i>doing nothing. That's what tires me out.</i>	
6					<i>Inactivity has led to my body losing its momentum, all that. Because we weren't doing any sport, obviously. So there you go, that's had a bit of an impact on all that.</i>	
9					<i>The less effort you put in, the more tired you get – that's certain too</i>	
11					<i>It's the fatigue of just being, of doing nothing too, and then when you're not active, you've got nothing to do.</i>	
12					<i>A sedentary lifestyle too, it's not...[...] It tends to make you feel a bit... a bit sluggish, all that.</i>	
12	<i>What could be causing your tiredness? Participant: It's that. Inactivity, actually.</i>					

	Daily living/routines	33.3	3	<i>Missing a meal, too.</i>
			4	<i>But the whole daily routine is very, very, very tiring</i>
			4	<i>Yes, it takes a lot of energy because... as I was saying, choosing what to eat, and also eating... I sort of slow down when I eat, and then, with the clock ticking and the time we have to eat, it puts a bit of pressure on me.</i>
			4	<i>It tires me out to have a shower, to do activities... well, to have a shower, to make my bed,</i>
			4	<i>And reading or even listening to music—just doing it—is exhausting.</i>
			4	<i>It's exhausting, because I do pottery, I do art, I do sport, I do all that. And it takes a huge amount of energy, and on top of that, it's the end of the week, so I... I feel a lot less energy than...</i>
			7	<i>Forcing myself to do things. Forcing myself... But afterwards, I'm glad I did it, you know.</i>
			9	<i>Lifestyle.</i>
			9	<i>Not going to bed at... lifestyle, you know.</i>
	Unknown causes	16.7	4	<i>I don't know where this fatigue comes from.</i>
			4	<i>I don't know if it's the medication or if it's the illness.</i>
			4	<i>No, I've no idea.</i>
			6	<i>Oh dear. (...) I don't know</i>

Supplementary table 2 : Causes of fatigue in people with schizophrenia with participants' quotes

Themes	Main categories	Categories	Participants per category (%)	Participant	Quote
Distinction between fatigue and other symptoms	Fatigue is different from amotivation		25	4	<i>Lack of motivation is like saying, 'I could do that, but at the same time, I don't feel like it; I want to rest.' But fatigue is 'I can't.</i>
				4	<i>But a lack of motivation isn't... a feeling of heaviness or anything like that. It's just a feeling of telling yourself, 'I could do this, but I'm not doing it'. But when you're tired, you say, 'I can't take any more, I can't do this, I've had enough'. So you stop.</i>
				5	<i>Lack of motivation: I don't know what to do. It's not natural tiredness, let's say.</i>
				7	<i>A lack of motivation—you don't feel like doing things for various reasons, you know. Well, everyone has their own reason. [...] With fatigue, you just can't really do it, you know.</i>
	Fatigue is different from anxiety		8.3	4	<i>It's more like stress... which is confused with... it's more on the physical side that you feel the anxiety, the stress, the fear.</i>
				4	<i>It's mainly a sense of weariness. But anxiety, it can really take over the whole... because fatigue is mental too. [...] But anxiety, it can take over the whole body and it can cause... involuntary reactions... in the body.</i>
				4	<i>Anxiety is more like fear.</i>
	Fatigue is different from apathy		16.7	1	<i>Fatigue is physical and apathy is more of a symptom.</i>
				6	<i>It doesn't actually atrophy that part of me.</i>
				6	<i>Fatigue doesn't stop you from feeling emotions.</i>
	Fatigue is different from depression		50	2	<i>Fatigue is temporary.</i>
				5	<i>Oh no, depression and fatigue don't have much to do with each other.</i>
				5	<i>Fatigue is mild compared to depression.</i>
				5	<i>Being tired is less serious than depression</i>
				6	<i>Depression is when you feel bad. Fatigue is when you feel tired.</i>
				7	<i>When you're depressed, you don't feel like doing anything. It's more psychological, really.</i>
11	<i>There's a kind of sadness there, too</i>				

Similarities/confusion	Fatigue is different from laziness	16.7	12	<i>Depression is... it doesn't just go away like that, you know. It's not enough to just go... When you're tired, you go to sleep and then you feel better, but... But depression doesn't just go away like that.</i>
			4	<i>You know you can do something, but you don't make the effort to do it.</i>
			5	<i>Well, I'd say laziness is the feeling of... "I'm feeling sluggish, I want to go and lie down". [...] And tiredness is... (...) I don't know how... (...) Tiredness is healthier, let's say.</i>
			5	<i>It's ok, but it's there... more naturally, let's say. [...] Whereas laziness is... I don't feel like it, I'm moping about and I keep feeling lazy</i>
			5	<i>It's being tired, tired, without knowing what to do to stop being tired. Whereas laziness stems from another bout of laziness, well, I don't know how to put it</i>
	Fatigue is different from sedation	41.7	2	<i>straight after being sedated, you're, you feel the sedation, let's say. And whereas tiredness, you feel that straight away too, but it can last longer if you're not careful</i>
			2	<i>Through the action of the sedation, shall we say.</i>
			5	<i>Sedation is through medication. Whereas tiredness can be natural – tired, I don't know, from having been for a walk; when you get back, you're tired.</i>
			6	<i>Before, the medication, yes. Then, the medication is sedation.</i>
			6	<i>Sedation comes from the effects of the medication. And fatigue is everything else</i>
			7	<i>Because I can see it when I'm tired all day and when I take the medication, I go to bed. Well, there really is an effect, the effect of the medication.</i>
			8	<i>The sedation takes over. Then you're knocked out. And sleep, that's natural. Actually, sleep—real sleep—isn't the sedation that... (...) That forces you to sleep. [...] Sedation isn't natural.</i>
	Fatigue is different from cognitive disorders	25	1	<i>It's more about intellectual capacity.</i>
			5	<i>I don't think it's... It's not tiredness, it's something else.</i>
			6	<i>Fatigue isn't to blame, so to speak; it's not always the case – it can happen – but it isn't always to blame for our memory lapses</i>
Fatigue is similar to amotivation	66.7	2	<i>When you're tired, you can lack motivation, of course.</i>	
		3	<i>I think you're not motivated and all that. I think tiredness can be a symptom of that.</i>	

			3	<i>No, it's pretty much the same thing too.</i>
			3	<i>If we're not motivated for that, often it might be because we don't feel like it, but it might also be because we're too tired</i>
			4	<i>"I'm motivated" means... I'd say it's not just that I'm tired, because being tired is really a feeling of exhaustion. It can be a feeling of exhaustion that tells us we can't do those things anymore because we've got no energy.</i>
			5	<i>It can be a sort of tiredness. Or just laziness, as I was explaining earlier.</i>
			6	<i>When you lack motivation, sometimes you can blame it on tiredness. It's simpler. It's a mental shortcut to tell yourself, no, no, it's fine</i>
			9	<i>Researcher : are lack of motivation and tiredness two different things? Participant : No</i>
			10	<i>Yes, I do confuse them.</i>
			11	<i>If you don't realise [amotivation] is a symptom, you might well just think you're tired</i>
	Fatigue is similar to anxiety/fear	8.3	4	<i>Anxiety.</i>
			4	<i>Apprehension</i>
			4	<i>Fear.</i>
Fatigue is similar to apathy	8.3	2	<i>Well, for me, I actually confuse it with tiredness.</i>	
		2	<i>That's abnegation, and you can confuse it with tiredness.</i>	
Fatigue is similar to depression	58.3	1	<i>They're different concepts but they're linked.</i>	
		1	<i>Because one can affect the other</i>	
		3	<i>Naturally, if there's depression, there's fatigue afterwards. It's inevitable. And there, yes, I think that if you're depressed, you're bound to feel tired to some extent.</i>	
		3	<i>there's a link with it, actually.</i>	
		3	<i>And, if there's depression, there's a lack of motivation, so there's definitely going to be fatigue.</i>	
		3	<i>The fact that you don't feel like doing anything anymore. You give up on a lot of things. Not seeing your friends anymore, not getting enough sleep at night. That makes us feel depressed and leaves us a bit... lacking in energy and all that.</i>	

			5	<i>Depression, maybe that's what makes you tired</i>
			7	<i>Well, you don't feel like doing anything. [...] So, it looks like symptoms of fatigue.</i>
			10	<i>When I'm feeling depressed, I'm mentally exhausted</i>
			11	<i>Yes. I've had very severe bouts of depression in the past. Interviewer: OK. And did it feel like fatigue? Well, were they things you could confuse, in the end? Participant: Yes. And then, it also made me stay in bed or...</i>
			11	<i>maybe... at the time I didn't realise it was depression, actually</i>
			12	<i>When you're depressed, it's the same, you sleep, you spend the day in bed.</i>
	Fatigue is similar to emotional numbness	8.3	11	<i>Researcher: In what way do you think these two things are similar? Participant: In the lack of pleasure, actually, in life.</i>
	Fatigue is similar to laziness	25	4	<i>A sort of laziness</i>
			5	<i>Fatigue, I don't know, it goes hand in hand with laziness</i>
			5	<i>Laziness makes me feel tired, actually. Tired of doing nothing.</i>
			6	<i>Laziness, fatigue – sometimes it's complicated</i>
	Fatigue is similar to physical manifestations of illness	8.3	3	<i>Having the flu or a fever.</i>
			3	<i>That's the crux of the tiredness when you have the flu or a fever. You have to look after yourself, rest, because it's a bit like the tiredness you might feel... that bad sort of fatigue.</i>
	Fatigue is similar to sedation	66.7	1	<i>It's the human body that isn't fully awake, I don't know.</i>
			1	<i>It feels similar.</i>
			2	<i>The medication was making me feel sedated, and I felt as though I was fatigued</i>
			2	<i>It actually feels like tiredness</i>
			3	<i>Yes. And that would be the good kind of tiredness.</i>
3			<i>Of course, yes, I think there's a connection with that.</i>	

			3	<i>I think the fact of being sedated is tiring in the long run</i>			
			4	<i>It's sedation, yes, I'm a bit sedated, I'm a bit out of it, I'm tired, I can't take it anymore.</i>			
			4	<i>For me, when I take the medication, I'm knocked out.</i>			
			4	<i>Researcher : so, for you, you can't really tell the difference between sedation and tiredness? //Participant: No.</i>			
			5	<i>Yes, I think they're very similar, that's it</i>			
			5	<i>it doesn't start the same way, but they're similar, I think, anyway, well, it's about being, it's a bit drowsy, isn't it, sedated.</i>			
			7	<i>I notice it when I take a medicine. For example, Loxapac – at first, they gave me 50 drops in the morning. I'd just go straight to sleep, basically.</i>			
			9	<i>No, there aren't any. [...] You feel like sleeping. [...] Sedation equals tiredness, tiredness equals sedation</i>			
			9	<i>I say sleepy instead of tired. I can't quite put my finger on it, it's really odd.</i>			
			12	<i>Researcher: Why do you confuse them? Participant: Because it's... it's the pills that knock you out, you see.</i>			
			12	<i>It's a bit like the side effects of the pills, really.</i>			
			Fatigue is similar to negative symptoms		25	1	<i>Because often, when I speak, it upsets me, actually. (.....) It upsets me, I'm upset.</i>
						2	<i>They could be confused with tiredness, more or less, because it depends on how you interpret it.</i>
2	<i>I think, the negative symptoms.</i>						
11	<i>Negative symptoms may resemble fatigue</i>						
Fatigue is similar to cognitive disorders	Memory disorders	16.7	3	<i>And fatigue can also cause memory problems, I think</i>			
			5	<i>When you're too tired, you start getting memory lapses.</i>			
	Attention disorders	41.7	2	<i>Fatigue can cause attention problems, I think</i>			
			3	<i>Yes, the fact, I think, that you find yourself in the city or somewhere, with lots of people around you. I think there are lots of sounds, all that, activity all around, that's it. All that, taking all that into account for the brain, is tiring too</i>			

				4	<i>when you're concentrating on something, well, as I was saying, it's tiring to concentrate on a task.</i>
				4	<i>When you're doing something, for example, in art class when you're drawing, and then someone else is talking at the same time, it's very hard to... to focus on something. [...] Especially over the long term. Researcher: Right. And so, does that require an effort on your part? Participant: Yes, and it's exhausting.</i>
				7	<i>Physical fatigue and attention problems—it's more that you just can't do it; it's mental, really.</i>
				7	<i>Dozing off, being exhausted—you stop listening to what people are saying.</i>
				9	<i>Researcher: Are there perhaps other symptoms of schizophrenia, for example, that could be confused with fatigue? Participant: Loss of concentration.</i>
				9	<i>Researcher: Are there any similarities between attention problems and fatigue? Participant: Oh yeah, absolutely</i>
				3	<i>It's very psychological, I think; it takes energy.</i>
	Unspecific cognitive disorders	33.3	3	<i>The activity, too much mental overload.</i>	
			4	<i>But when it's something else that's a bit more complicated, well, you can feel exhausted.</i>	
			6	<i>My mental slowdown.</i>	
			6	<i>I don't know if I don't do it because I'm not mentally capable of doing it due to my mental decline. [...] Or I don't do it because I'm already tired at the thought of what it's going to take.</i>	
			6	<i>When I can't bring myself to make the effort for a task that requires me to think, I sometimes tend to mix up the idea of... "I don't know how to do it, so I'm not going to do it" or "I don't feel like doing it because I feel it's going to tire me out".</i>	
			12	<i>Researcher: And so, could that be mistaken for just a bit of cognitive impairment? Participant: Yes</i>	

Supplementary table 3 : Distinction between fatigue and other symptoms in people with schizophrenia with participants' quotes